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Abstract

A new generalized upper bound solution for the ECAE process is presented in this paper. Using mathematical definition of Bezier curves a streamline was formulated to define a generalized deforming region. Based on this deforming region a kinematically admissible velocity field was obtained from which upper bound solutions were computed. By changing the parameters defining the Bezier shaped streamline which in turn defines the deforming region the optimization of the upper bound solution was carried out. Equal channel angular extrusion through 90 degrees bend was considered. Using the formulation presented in here it was possible to predict the shape of the dead metal zone and its variation with frictional conditions. Unlike previous work in which a fixed circular shape had been assumed for the dead metal zone, in this paper a generalized shaped Bezier curve was used. The optimum value of the extrusion pressure for ECAE was obtained and compared with both experimental and theoretical data from previous works. It was concluded that the present solution gave an improvement over all previous works and the author's results were closer to experimental data.

Keywords: ECAE, Upper Bound, Velocity Field, Bezier Curves, Dead Metal Zone.

Nomenclature

x_i, y_i	The coordinate of point p_i defining Bezier characteristic polygon
$\psi, \psi_1, \psi_2, \text{ and } \psi_3$	Angles shown in Fig.2
$v, w, \text{ and } r$	Parameters used for optimizing upper bound solution
$a, b, \text{ and } h$	Parameters defining die geometry shown in Fig.2
ϕ	Die bend angle

v_0	Velocity of material in zone I and IV
t	Parameter determining the position of the particle on a streamline
u	Parameter determining the position of the particle on channel width
X, Y	The coordinate of a particle in the deforming zone or the parametric coordinate of Bezier curves
v_x, v_y	Components of velocity field
$\dot{\varepsilon}_x, \dot{\varepsilon}_y, \text{ and } \dot{\tau}_{xy}$	Components of strain rate in deforming zone
$\dot{W}$	The power dissipated during the process
F	The force applied during the process
$\bar{y}_0, y_0$	The average yield stress, the yield stress
m	The friction constant
α	The acute angle between the tangent of streamline and the y axis
ε_{ave}	Total equivalent strain induced during process
ε_{stream}	Equivalent strain induced in deforming zone
$\varepsilon_{si}, \varepsilon_{so}, \text{ and } \varepsilon_s$	Equivalent strains induced in entry and exit discontinuity surfaces, sum of ε_{si} and ε_{so}
γ_i and γ_o	Shear strains induced in entry and exit discontinuity surfaces
$ \Delta v $	Velocity discontinuity
l_i, l_o	Instant length of the specimen in the entry and exit channel before point A and after point B
v_{d0}	Initial velocity in deforming region on the entry discontinuity surface
C	Constant for the velocity field equations to be determined from the boundary conditions

Introduction

In recent years materials and products with micro and nano-size grains have attracted a lot of attention and researchers have tried to come up with new and effective solutions. Equal channel angular extrusion has been the center of activities in this respect. In this

process usually the material does not undergo any reduction of area but the grain size is reduced due to the deformation through the angular movement in the extrusion die.

Altan et al [1] analyzed the deformation of the material during a 90° equal-channel angular extrusion (ECAE) process using upper-bound theorem. They suggested a model which included the effect of friction between the sample and the die walls, radius of inner corner of the die and the dead metal zone on the deformation patterns during ECAE.

Eivani and Karimi Taheri [2] analyzed deformation of material in equal channel angular extrusion (ECAE) process with outer curved corner using an upper bound solution. They considered the effects of die angle, friction between the sample and the die walls, and the angle of the outer curved corner, on the extrusion pressure. Sandim et al [3] deformed Niobium single crystals by equal channel angular extrusion (ECAE) with one, four, and eight passes at room temperature. They found that the microstructure of the sample deformed after one ECAE pass and displayed uniformly spaced coarse parallel sets of shear bands. In the most deformed specimen (eight ECAE passes), the microstructure was observed to be more uniform and consisted of fine grains with sizes of about 1 micro meter. Li et al [4] investigated the microstructure and texture evolution in interstitial-free steel during ECAE using a 120 degree die for up to four passes via three routes. They used finite element simulation to help understand deformation behavior and texture formation. It was found that the efficiency of grain refinement was to be only mildly dependent on die angle and processing route. Zhang et al [5] simulated the plastic deformation of commercially pure (CP) titanium by multi-pass equal channel angular extrusion (ECAE), at medium hot-working temperature, using finite element method. They found that unlike the single ECAE pass, where the corner gap was important, it was the repetitive billet-end side-shift of less-deformed billet-ends which were responsible for the development of the non-uniformly deformed zone in the multi-pass ECAE process. Tham et al [6] conducted an experimental study on multi-pass ECAE process of a widely used aluminum 6061 alloy. They found out that there was a significant increase in the strain hardening exponent of the samples subjected to the different heat treatment configurations due to severe plastic deformation after multi-pass ECAE. Petryk and Stupkiewicz [7] studied the effect of severe plastic deformation (SPD) on grain refinement and strain hardening in polycrystalline metals. The decrease in size of dislocation cells and cell-blocks was expressed as a function of the effective plastic strain influenced by strain-rate reversals. The proposed model was claimed to provide a tool for quantitative comparison of different SPD processes. Kecskes et al [8] presented two

general methodologies for the production of ultrafine grained (UFG) and nanocrystalline (NC) tungsten (W) metal samples namely the top-down and bottom-up. They used ECAE coupled with rolling to fabricate UFG W. They also conducted a series of bottom-up experiments to consolidate powdered UFG W precursors into solid bodies. The bottom-up approach relied on rapid, high-temperature consolidation, specifically designed for UFG and NCW powders.

Su et al [9] investigated the AZ31 Mg alloy samples processed by the equal channel angular pressing (ECAP) process at 200 °C for up to four passes. They studied the microstructural evolution during ECAP using optical microscope and transmission electron microscope. They proposed a model for the grain refinement mechanism of Mg during ECAP, using data observed from the microstructure analysis. Hasani et al [10] analyzed the flow lines in aluminium alloy 6061 during equal channel angular extrusion (ECAE) in a 90° die with and without the application of back pressure during pressing. They showed that back pressure slightly lowers the total strain, strongly increases the size of the plastic zone and significantly reduces the plastic strain rate. Eivani and Karimi Taheri [11], studied the deformation of material during equal channel angular extrusion (ECAE) using an upper bound model. They considered the effect of die angle and friction between the sample and the die walls on the geometry of dead metal zone and total strain. The relationship between the friction coefficient, the extent of dead metal zone and total strain was derived.

A new formulation is presented in this paper for the ECAE process which uses a Bezier shaped curve to define a general streamline. The deforming region is defined and optimized to minimize the upper bound on the extrusion pressure.

Theory

The geometry of the ECAE die is shown in figure (1). The parameters defining the deforming geometry are illustrated in figure (2). Plane strain deformation has been assumed for the theoretical analysis presented here. In this geometry the inner corner of the ECAE die (arc $D'CE'$) has been assumed to be defined by a Bezier curve. The outer surface of the die has a sharp corner (point C) and hence the material during deformation forms a dead metal zone in this area. The interface of the dead metal zone and the deforming region is defined by a streamline in the shape of a third degree Bezier curve. All streamlines in the deforming regions are in fact symmetric with respect to line OC. Referring to figure (2) the size of the streamline diminishes as one moves from the interface of the dead metal zone towards the

inner corner of the die. Therefore by defining a particle moving on a general streamline all points in the deforming region are defined.

In the present analysis four distinct regions have been defined in the ECAE: region (I) where the material moves in a rigid manner before coming into contact with line OD where the deformation begins; region (II) defined by the boundaries $D'DEE'G'CFD'$ which is the deforming zone; region III between lines DCE and arc DE which forms the dead metal zone; and finally region IV where the material after leaving the deforming region at line OE moves as a rigid body.

As mentioned earlier the deforming region in this analysis has been formulated by a single equation defining a Bezier curve. Mathematically, for $n+1$ control points, the Bezier curve is defined by the following polynomial with n degrees:

$$P(t) = \sum_{i=0}^n P_i B_{i,n}(t) \quad 0 \leq t \leq 1 \quad (1)$$

Where $P(t)$ any is a point on the curve and P_i is a control point. $B_{i,n}$ are the Bernstein polynomials:

$$B_{i,n}(t) = D(n,i) t^i (1-t)^{n-i} \quad (2)$$

Where $D(n,i)$ is:

$$D(n,i) = \frac{n!}{i!(n-i)!} \quad (3)$$

Therefore a Bezier curve with four control points as used in this paper can be expressed as follows:

$$P(t) = P_0(1-t)^3 + 3P_1t(1-t)^2 + 3P_2t^2(1-t) + P_3t^3 \quad 0 \leq t \leq 1 \quad (4)$$

To define such curves consider a particle at a distance x from point O (figure (2)), moving on a streamline. Points P_1, P_2, P_3 and P_4 in figure (2) define the characteristics of a Bezier curve.

The coordinates of these points ($x_1, y_1, x_2, y_2, x_3, y_3, x_4$ and y_4) are defined as follows:

Defining the line p_1p_2 (figure (2)) we have:

$$y - y_1 = -(\cot \psi_3)(x - x_1) \quad (5)$$

Line OF (figure (2)) also is defined as:

$$y = (\tan \psi_2)x \quad (6)$$

From the intersection of these two lines we have:

$$x_2 = \frac{x_1 + \frac{y_1}{\cot \psi_3}}{\frac{\tan \psi_2}{\cot \psi_3} + 1} \quad (7)$$

Therefore:

$$y_2 = \left(\frac{x_1 + \frac{y_1}{\cot \psi_3}}{\frac{\tan \psi_2}{\cot \psi_3} + 1} \right) \tan \psi_2 \quad (8)$$

Similarly the equation of line p_3p_4 is given by:

$$y - y_4 = -\cot(\psi - \psi_3)(x - x_4) \quad (9)$$

And line OG is defined as:

$$y = x \tan(\psi - \psi_2) \quad (10)$$

Intersecting these two lines we have:

$$x_3 = \frac{x_4 \cot(\psi - \psi_3) + y_4}{\tan(\psi - \psi_2) + \cot(\psi - \psi_3)} \quad (11)$$

Therefore:

$$y_3 = \left(\frac{x_4 \cot(\psi - \psi_3) + y_4}{\tan(\psi - \psi_2) + \cot(\psi - \psi_3)} \right) \tan(\psi - \psi_2) \quad (12)$$

The coordinates of points p_1 and p_4 are given by:

$$x_1 = x, \quad y_1 = x \tan \psi_1 \quad (13)$$

$$x_4 = \frac{x}{\cos \psi_1} \cos(\psi - \psi_1), \quad y_4 = \frac{x}{\cos \psi_1} \sin(\psi - \psi_1) \quad (14)$$

$$0 \leq \psi_1 < \frac{\psi}{2}, \psi_1 < \psi_2 \leq \frac{\psi}{2}, 0 \leq \psi_3 \leq \frac{\psi}{2} \quad (15)$$

In order to transform the above parameters into dimensionless parameters use the following:

$$\begin{cases} \frac{x}{h} = u \Rightarrow x = uh \\ \frac{\psi_1}{\frac{\psi}{2}} = v \Rightarrow \psi_1 = \frac{v\psi}{2} \\ \frac{\psi_2}{\frac{\psi}{2}} = w \Rightarrow \psi_2 = \frac{w\psi}{2} \\ \frac{\psi_3}{\frac{\psi}{2}} = r \Rightarrow \psi_3 = \frac{r\psi}{2} \end{cases} \quad (16)$$

$$\frac{b}{h} \leq u \leq 1, 0 \leq v < 1, v < w \leq 1, 0 \leq r \leq 1$$

Now substituting (16) into (7), (8), (11), (12), (13) and (14) the coordinates of points P_1 , P_2 , P_3 and P_4 are expressed as follow:

$$x_1 = uh \quad , \quad y_1 = uh \tan\left(\frac{v\psi}{2}\right) \quad (17)$$

$$x_2 = \frac{x_1 + \frac{y_1}{\cot\left(\frac{r\psi}{2}\right)}}{\frac{\tan\left(\frac{w\psi}{2}\right)}{\cot\left(\frac{r\psi}{2}\right)} + 1} \quad , \quad y_2 = x_2 \tan\left(\frac{w\psi}{2}\right) \quad (18)$$

$$x_3 = \frac{x_4 \cot\left(\left(1 - \frac{r}{2}\right)\psi\right) + y_4}{\tan\left(\left(1 - \frac{w}{2}\right)\psi\right) + \cot\left(\left(1 - \frac{r}{2}\right)\psi\right)} \quad , \quad y_3 = x_3 \tan\left(\left(1 - \frac{w}{2}\right)\psi\right)$$

(19)

$$x_4 = \frac{uh}{\cos\left(\frac{v\psi}{2}\right)} \cos\left(\left(1 - \frac{v}{2}\right)\psi\right) \quad , \quad y_4 = \frac{uh}{\cos\left(\frac{v\psi}{2}\right)} \sin\left(\left(1 - \frac{v}{2}\right)\psi\right) \quad (20)$$

Now a third degree equation defining the Bezier curve using the above characteristics is defined by equation (4). The value of t determines the position of the particle on a streamline.

Using equations (5) and (6) the Cartesian coordinates of the particle are generally defined as:

$$X(t) = x_1(1-t)^3 + 3x_2t(1-t)^2 + 3x_3t^2(1-t) + x_4t^3 \quad (21)$$

$$Y(t) = y_1(1-t)^3 + 3y_2t(1-t)^2 + 3y_3t^2(1-t) + y_4t^3 \quad (22)$$

Now if in equations (21) and (22) substitutions are made for $x_1, y_1, x_2, y_2, x_3, y_3, x_4$ and y_4 from equations (17), (18), (19) and (20) then the coordinates X and Y are defined in terms of v, w and r . By varying the parameters v, w and r , the shape of the Bezier curves - equation (4) - (i.e. the streamlines) could be changed. This means that by varying v, w and r , the deforming region changes and hence these parameters could later be used in the optimization process.

To formulate a general kinematically admissible velocity field the method of reference [12] has been modified, the details of which are given in appendix-A (see figure (3)). Therefore the velocity components for the deforming region of figure (2) are given as:

$$v_x = \frac{C}{Y_t X_u - Y_u X_t} X_t$$

$$v_y = \frac{C}{Y_t X_u - Y_u X_t} Y_t \quad (23)$$

where C is given by:

$$C = \frac{v_0 h \left(\cot\left(\frac{r\psi}{2}\right) + \tan\left(\frac{v\psi}{2}\right) \right) \cos\left(\frac{v\psi}{2}\right) \cos\left(\frac{r\psi}{2}\right)}{\cos\left(\frac{r\psi}{2}\right) \cos\left((v-r)\frac{\psi}{2}\right)} \quad (24)$$

Now using the above velocity field and the coordinate transformation in appendix-A (equations A-9 to A-12) the strain rate components are readily derived using the following relations:

$$\dot{\epsilon}_x = \frac{\partial v_x}{\partial x}, \dot{\epsilon}_y = \frac{\partial v_y}{\partial y}$$

$$\dot{\epsilon}_{xy} = \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{\partial v_x}{\partial y} + \frac{\partial v_y}{\partial x} \right) \quad (25)$$

Using the above strain rate components the total power for the ECAE process is obtained as follows:

$$\dot{W}_{total} = \dot{W}_i + \dot{W}_{f1} + \dot{W}_{f2} + \dot{W}_{f3} + \dot{W}_l + \dot{W}_{si} + \dot{W}_{so} \quad (26)$$

The details for computing the different components of the total power have been outlined in appendix-B. Having calculated the total power for the ECAE process the extrusion force and pressure are found by:

$$\dot{W}_{total} = F \times v_0 \quad (27)$$

Now the above formulation applies to any metallic material and if the work hardening behaviour of the material is to be taken into account then a simple strain hardening rule such as the one given below is used:

$$\bar{\sigma} = k \bar{\epsilon}^n \quad (28)$$

To obtain a value for y_0 which is used in appendix (C), the following integration is carried out along a streamline:

$$\bar{y}_0 = \frac{\int_0^{\bar{\epsilon}_{ave}} \bar{\sigma} d\epsilon}{\int_0^{\bar{\epsilon}_{ave}} d\epsilon} = \frac{\int_0^{\bar{\epsilon}_{ave}} k \epsilon^n d\epsilon}{\bar{\epsilon}_{ave}} \quad (29)$$

Results and Discussions:

The extrusion of aluminium alloy 2024 was analyzed through a 90 degree bend die (figure (1)) using the formulation proposed by the authors. First of all the shape of the dead metal zone was obtained so that all the surfaces bounding the deforming region were determined. The analysis was carried out using the upper bound analysis for a typical 90 degree bend die (figure (1)) with $a = 0.014m$ and $b = 0.0005m$ (figure (2)). The interface between the dead metal zone and the deforming region as determined by the present analysis is observed in figure (4). A typical flow line has also been shown in the same figure. Theoretical values for normalized extrusion pressure for ECAE through different die angles are shown in figure (5) for various frictional conditions. Clearly as the bend angle becomes steeper, the pressure increases. The behaviour of the normalized pressure is linear with respect to die angle values.

Using the present analysis optimization of the upper bound results was carried out and the effect of frictional conditions on the position of the entry velocity discontinuity surface to the deforming region is shown in figure (6). These results are shown for different die bend angles. In general, higher friction factors cause the entry velocity discontinuity surface to become more horizontal. For higher die bend angle the effect of friction on the entry velocity discontinuity was more pronounced. In figure (7) the theoretical predictions of the equivalent strains for different die angles could be seen under different frictional conditions. It is clear that frictional conditions do not have great influence on the strain especially at higher die angles. However for smaller die angles higher values of strains are obtained. Another interesting result obtained from the analysis was the effect of the frictional conditions on the geometry of deforming region which is illustrated in figure (8). It could be seen that under more severe frictional conditions the deforming region extends and as the friction factor decreases, it becomes smaller.

Influence of the internal bend radius of the die on the extrusion pressure and effective strain is shown in figure (9). As far as the normalized extrusion pressure is concerned sharper bends mean lower pressure and in general as the bend radius increases the normalized pressure increases slightly from about 2.45 for a sharp corner to 3 for a value of $b=0.02m$. The same trend could be observed for the equivalent strain except that the change in strain is more pronounced as the bend radius increases. This may be explained by the fact that as the bend radius increases the material has to flow over a bigger surface thereby expending more energy.

In order to verify the results of the present analysis experimental results from references [1], [2] and [11] have been used. The internal bend radius of the die has been taken as small as possible to simulate a sharp corner. Therefore the analysis was carried out for a die angle $\varphi = 90^\circ$, channel length $l = 66mm$, channel width $a=14mm$, friction factor, $m=0.18$, material yield strength of 179.3MPa and strain hardening exponent $n=0.26$, so the deforming region was obtained as shown in figure (10) with DEC as the dead metal zone. Using these data in figure (11) the comparison of authors' results with both experimental and theoretical data from previous work are shown. It could be observed that the results predicted by the present formulations show improvements with regards to previous theoretical work while it also agrees well with the experimental data.

Conclusions

-A new formulation was developed based on upper bound theorem for the analysis of ECAE process. This new formulation is more general and much improved with respect to previous work as it does not make many assumptions and simplifications made in them.

-The deforming region was defined in a general way so that when minimizing the upper bound the shape of the deforming region was optimized to become as close as possible to the real situation. This general definition of the deforming region gave this formulation an advantage over previous work which had used fixed deforming regions.

-By the optimization process of the upper bound formulation the shape of the dead metal zone was predicted and the effect of friction simulated. Again in the formulation presented here a generalized Bezier curve was taken for the boundary of the dead metal zone while in previous work a circular boundary was assumed.

-The relative extrusion pressure computed from the present theory was yet the closest to the experimental data as compared with previous works.

-Using the present formulation a die design (bend angle, inner and outer bend radius,) was obtained where larger strains were experienced in one pass while the increase in the extrusion pressure was not significant.

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Appendix A

A general kinematically admissible velocity field

With reference to [12] and considering that in this paper a plane strain deformation has been assumed, the equation of the tangent at a general point in the deforming region is defined by:

$$\vec{r}_t = X_t \vec{i} + Y_t \vec{j} \quad (\text{A.1})$$

Since this point is placed on a streamline (see figure (2)) then its velocity is defined by:

$$\vec{v} = v_x \vec{i} + v_y \vec{j} \quad (\text{A.2})$$

The two vectors are parallel which means:

$$\frac{v_x}{X_t} = \frac{v_y}{Y_t} \Rightarrow v_x = \frac{X_t}{Y_t} v_y \quad (\text{A.3})$$

The above equation should satisfy the condition for incompressibility:

$$\frac{\partial v_x}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial v_y}{\partial y} = 0 \quad (\text{A.4})$$

On the other hand since X and Y are defined in terms of u and t then the following transformation should be used to obtain the velocity components:

$$\begin{bmatrix} \frac{\partial v_x}{\partial x} & \frac{\partial v_x}{\partial y} \\ \frac{\partial v_y}{\partial x} & \frac{\partial v_y}{\partial y} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{\partial v_x}{\partial u} & \frac{\partial v_x}{\partial t} \\ \frac{\partial v_y}{\partial u} & \frac{\partial v_y}{\partial t} \end{bmatrix} \times \begin{bmatrix} \frac{\partial u}{\partial x} & \frac{\partial u}{\partial y} \\ \frac{\partial t}{\partial x} & \frac{\partial t}{\partial y} \end{bmatrix} \quad (\text{A.5})$$

Using the determinant j and its inverse we have:

$$j = \begin{bmatrix} X_u & X_t \\ Y_u & Y_t \end{bmatrix} \quad (\text{A.6})$$

$$j^{-1} = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{\partial u}{\partial x} & \frac{\partial u}{\partial y} \\ \frac{\partial t}{\partial x} & \frac{\partial t}{\partial y} \end{bmatrix} \quad (\text{A.7})$$

Hence the following expression is obtained:

$$\begin{bmatrix} \frac{\partial v_x}{\partial x} & \frac{\partial v_x}{\partial y} \\ \frac{\partial v_y}{\partial x} & \frac{\partial v_y}{\partial y} \end{bmatrix} = \frac{1}{\det j} \begin{bmatrix} \frac{\partial v_x}{\partial u} & \frac{\partial v_x}{\partial t} \\ \frac{\partial v_y}{\partial u} & \frac{\partial v_y}{\partial t} \end{bmatrix} \times \begin{bmatrix} Y_t & -X_t \\ -Y_u & X_u \end{bmatrix} \quad (\text{A.8})$$

Therefore from (A.8) the following components for the derivatives of the velocity components are derived:

$$\frac{\partial v_x}{\partial x} = \frac{1}{\det j} \left(\frac{\partial v_x}{\partial u} Y_t - \frac{\partial v_x}{\partial t} Y_u \right) \quad (\text{A.9})$$

$$\frac{\partial v_x}{\partial y} = \frac{1}{\det j} \left(-\frac{\partial v_x}{\partial u} X_t + \frac{\partial v_x}{\partial t} X_u \right) \quad (\text{A.10})$$

$$\frac{\partial v_y}{\partial x} = \frac{1}{\det j} \left(\frac{\partial v_y}{\partial u} Y_t - \frac{\partial v_y}{\partial t} Y_u \right) \quad (\text{A.11})$$

$$\frac{\partial v_y}{\partial y} = \frac{1}{\det j} \left(-\frac{\partial v_y}{\partial u} X_t + \frac{\partial v_y}{\partial t} X_u \right) \quad (\text{A.12})$$

Using the above components and substituting in the incompressibility equation (A.4) yields:

$$Y_t \frac{\partial v_x}{\partial u} - Y_u \frac{\partial v_x}{\partial t} - X_t \frac{\partial v_y}{\partial u} + X_u \frac{\partial v_y}{\partial t} = 0 \quad (\text{A.13})$$

Simplifying we have:

$$Y_t \left(\frac{(X_u v_y + X_t v_{yu}) Y_t - Y_u X_t v_y}{Y_t^2} \right) - Y_u \left(\frac{(X_u v_y + X_t v_{yt}) Y_t - Y_u X_t v_y}{Y_t^2} \right) - X_t v_{yu} + X_u v_{yt} = 0 \quad (\text{A.14})$$

Rearranging the above expression gives:

$$\underbrace{\left(X_u - \frac{Y_u}{Y_t} X_t - \frac{Y_u}{Y_t} X_u + \frac{Y_u}{Y_t^2} Y_u X_t \right)}_A v_y + \underbrace{\left(X_u - \frac{Y_u}{Y_t} X_t \right)}_B \frac{\partial v_y}{\partial t} = 0 \quad (\text{A.15})$$

Hence the following simple expression is obtained expressing (A.15) as:

$$A v_y + B \frac{\partial v_y}{\partial t} = 0 \quad (\text{A.16})$$

Noting that:

$$A = \frac{\partial B}{\partial t} \quad (\text{A.17})$$

Then (A.16) is re-written as:

$$\frac{\partial B}{\partial t} v_y + B \frac{\partial v_y}{\partial t} = 0 \quad (\text{A.18})$$

Rearranging (A.18) yields:

$$\frac{\partial v_y}{v_y} = -\frac{\partial B}{B} \quad (\text{A.19})$$

Integrating (A.19) gives:

$$\ln(v_y) = -\ln(B) + \ln C = \ln\left(\frac{C}{B}\right) \quad (\text{A.20})$$

Where:

$$v_y = \frac{C}{B} \quad (\text{A.21})$$

$$B = X_u - \frac{Y_u}{Y_t} X_t \quad (\text{A.22})$$

Velocity discontinuities at entry and exit: Considering figure (3) the direction of the initial velocity v_0 changes after entering the deforming region by an amount of ψ_3 and its magnitude becomes v_{d0} . By equating the components of the velocity perpendicular to the shear plane DD' we have:

$$v_{d0} \cos(\psi_3 - \psi_1) = v_0 \cos \psi_1 \Rightarrow v_{d0} = \frac{v_0 \cos \psi_1}{\cos(\psi_3 - \psi_1)} \Rightarrow v_{d0} = \frac{v_0 \cos\left(\frac{v\psi}{2}\right)}{\cos\left(\frac{(r-v)\psi}{2}\right)} \quad (\text{A.23})$$

The components of v_{d0} in x and y directions are:

$$v_{d0x} = -\frac{v_0 \cos\left(\frac{v\psi}{2}\right)}{\cos\left(\frac{(r-v)\psi}{2}\right)} \sin\left(\frac{r\psi}{2}\right) \quad (\text{A.24})$$

$$v_{d0y} = \frac{v_0 \cos\left(\frac{v\psi}{2}\right)}{\cos\left(\frac{(r-v)\psi}{2}\right)} \cos\left(\frac{r\psi}{2}\right) \quad (\text{A.25})$$

Therefore the velocity discontinuity along DD' is given by:

$$|\Delta v| = \left| \frac{v_0 \cos\left(\frac{v\psi}{2}\right)}{\cos\left(\frac{(r-v)\psi}{2}\right)} \sin\left(\frac{(r-v)\psi}{2}\right) + v_0 \sin\left(\frac{v\psi}{2}\right) \right| \quad (\text{A.26})$$

Considering equation (A.21) yields:

$$\begin{cases} t = 0 \Rightarrow v_y = v_{d0y} \Rightarrow v_y = \frac{C}{B} \\ t = 0 \Rightarrow B = B_{t=0} \end{cases} \quad (\text{A.27})$$

Hence a value is obtained for C as follows:

$$C = \frac{v_0 h \left(\cot\left(\frac{r\psi}{2}\right) + \tan\left(\frac{v\psi}{2}\right) \right) \cos\left(\frac{v\psi}{2}\right) \cos\left(\frac{r\psi}{2}\right)}{\cot\left(\frac{r\psi}{2}\right) \cos\left((v-r)\frac{\psi}{2}\right)} \quad (\text{A.28})$$

Note that in case of no velocity discontinuity $r = 0 \Rightarrow C = hv_0$.

Therefore by substituting (A.28) and (A.22) into (A.21) the general kinematically admissible velocity field is obtained as follows:

$$v_x = \frac{C}{Y_t X_u - Y_u X_t} X_t \quad (\text{A.29})$$

$$v_y = \frac{C}{Y_t X_u - Y_u X_t} Y_t \quad (\text{A.30})$$

Note that no matter what the deforming region is the general velocity field is always automatically admissible. This would be a great help when optimizing the upper bound solution.

Appendix B

Components of the ECAE total power

Having obtained the velocity and strain rate fields the components of the ECAE total power are determined as follows:

The power of internal deformation:

$$\left\{ \begin{aligned} \dot{W}_i &= \frac{2y_0 a}{\sqrt{3}} \int_0^1 \int_{\frac{b}{h}}^1 \left[\left(\frac{\dot{\epsilon}_x^2 + \dot{\epsilon}_y^2}{2} \right) + \dot{\epsilon}_{xy}^2 \right]^{\frac{1}{2}} \left| \frac{\partial(x, y)}{\partial(u, t)} \right| dt du \\ \left| \frac{\partial(x, y)}{\partial(u, t)} \right| &= \begin{vmatrix} \frac{\partial X}{\partial u} & \frac{\partial Y}{\partial u} \\ \frac{\partial X}{\partial t} & \frac{\partial Y}{\partial t} \end{vmatrix} = X_u Y_t - Y_u X_t \end{aligned} \right. \quad (\text{B.1})$$

The component of power due to the shear at the interface of the dead metal zone and the deforming region is given by:

$$\dot{W}_{f1} = \iint \tau_f |\Delta v| ds = \frac{m y_0}{\sqrt{3}} \iint (v_x^2 + v_y^2)^{\frac{1}{2}} \Big|_{u=1} ds \quad (\text{B.2})$$

Where

$$ds = a \frac{dy}{\cos \alpha} \quad (\text{B.3})$$

By substituting (B.3) into (B.2) and coordinate transformation:

$$\dot{W}_{f1} = \frac{m y_0 a}{\sqrt{3}} \int_0^1 (v_x^2 + v_y^2)^{\frac{1}{2}} \Big|_{u=1} \frac{1}{\cos \alpha} Y_t dt \quad (\text{B.4})$$

Where

$$\frac{1}{\cos \alpha} = \frac{1}{\vec{T} \cdot \vec{j}} \quad (\text{B.5})$$

Here $\vec{T}$ is the tangent vector to the streamline given by:

$$T(t) = \frac{1}{(X_t^2 + Y_t^2)^{\frac{1}{2}}} (X_t \vec{i} + Y_t \vec{j}) \quad (\text{B.6})$$

Therefore

$$\frac{1}{\cos \alpha} = \frac{(X_t^2 + Y_t^2)^{\frac{1}{2}}}{Y_t} \quad (\text{B.7})$$

Now substituting (B.7) into (B.4) and considering $m=1$ for the interface of the deforming region and the dead metal zone, the component of power dissipated due to the dead metal zone interface with the deforming region is given by:

$$\dot{W}_{f1} = \frac{y_0 a}{\sqrt{3}} \int_0^1 (v_x^2 + v_y^2)^{\frac{1}{2}} \Big|_{u=1} (X_t^2 + Y_t^2)^{\frac{1}{2}} \Big|_{u=1} dt \quad (\text{B.8})$$

The component of power due to velocity discontinuity at the inner surface of the die (figure (2)) is given by:

$$\dot{W}_{f2} = \frac{m y_0 a}{\sqrt{3}} \int_0^1 (v_x^2 + v_y^2)^{\frac{1}{2}} \Big|_{u=\frac{b}{h}} (X_t^2 + Y_t^2)^{\frac{1}{2}} \Big|_{u=\frac{b}{h}} dt \quad (\text{B.9})$$

where

$$\tau_0 = \frac{y_0}{\sqrt{3}}$$

The component of power due to velocity discontinuity at the interface of the deforming region and the die (figure (2)) – interfaces AD and EB is given by:

$$\dot{W}_{f3} = 2(m \tau_0 v_0 h \tan \psi_1 a) = 2m \tau_0 v_0 h a \tan\left(\frac{v\psi}{2}\right) \quad (\text{B.10})$$

The components of power due to velocity discontinuity at the interfaces of the rigid material region and the die (figure (2)) – before and after AA' and BB' where the material moves in a rigid fashion on the die surface- are given by:

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{W}_l(i) &= 4ma\tau_0 v_0 l_i \\ \dot{W}_l(o) &= 4ma\tau_0 v_0 l_o \end{aligned} \quad (\text{B.11})$$

The components of power due to velocity discontinuity at entry (DD') and exit surfaces (EE') of the deforming region (figure (2)) are given by:

$$\dot{W}_{si} = \dot{W}_{so} = \iint \tau_0 |\Delta v| ds = \frac{a y_0}{\sqrt{3}} \int |\Delta v| dl \quad (\text{B.12})$$

Now considering figure (2) note that:

$$\begin{aligned} dl \cos \psi_1 &= dx \\ dl &= \frac{dx}{\cos \psi_1} = \frac{dx}{\cos\left(\frac{v\psi}{2}\right)} \end{aligned} \quad (\text{B.13})$$

For point p_1 in the shear surface DD' we have:

$$x = uh \Rightarrow dx = hdu \quad (\text{B.14})$$

Substituting (B.14) into (B.13) gives:

$$dl = \frac{hdu}{\cos\left(\frac{v\psi}{2}\right)} \quad (\text{B.15})$$

Substituting (B.15) into (B.12) yields:

$$\dot{W}_{si} = \dot{W}_{so} = \frac{ay_0}{\sqrt{3}} \int_{\frac{b}{h}}^1 |\Delta v| \frac{hdu}{\cos\left(\frac{v\psi}{2}\right)} \quad (\text{B.16})$$

Substituting (A.26) into (B.16) and integrating gives:

$$\dot{W}_s = \dot{W}_{si} + \dot{W}_{so} = \frac{2}{\sqrt{3}} ahy_0v_0 \left(1 - \frac{b}{h}\right) \left(\tan\left(\left(r-v\right)\frac{\psi}{2}\right) + \tan\left(\frac{v\psi}{2}\right) \right) \quad (\text{B.17})$$

Appendix C

Average Strain

The equivalent or effective strain rate, in general is defined as:

$$\bar{\dot{\epsilon}} = \frac{2}{\sqrt{3}} \sqrt{\frac{1}{2} \dot{\epsilon}_{ij} \dot{\epsilon}_{ij}} = \frac{2}{\sqrt{3}} \left(\frac{\dot{\epsilon}_x^2 + \dot{\epsilon}_y^2 + \dot{\epsilon}_z^2 + 2\dot{\epsilon}_{xy}^2 + 2\dot{\epsilon}_{xz}^2 + 2\dot{\epsilon}_{yz}^2}{2} \right) \quad (C.1)$$

For the plane strain deformation we have:

$$\bar{\dot{\epsilon}} = \frac{2}{\sqrt{3}} \left(\frac{\dot{\epsilon}_x^2 + \dot{\epsilon}_y^2}{2} + \dot{\epsilon}_{xy}^2 \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} \quad (C.2)$$

Equivalent strain in the deforming region:

The effective strain is determined by integrating (C.2) with respect to time:

$$\bar{\epsilon} = \int \bar{\dot{\epsilon}} dt \quad (C.3)$$

Taking an element of distance ds on the streamline the velocity of a particle passing through that distance is given by:

$$\frac{ds}{dt} = v \quad \text{where } ds \cos \alpha = dy \quad \text{and} \quad \frac{1}{\cos \alpha} = \frac{(X_t^2 + Y_t^2)^{\frac{1}{2}}}{Y_t} \quad \text{hence:}$$

$$dt = \frac{1}{v} \frac{1}{\cos \alpha} dy = \frac{(X_t^2 + Y_t^2)^{\frac{1}{2}}}{Y_t (v_x^2 + v_y^2)^{\frac{1}{2}}} dy \quad (C.4)$$

Substituting (C.2) and (C.4) into (C.3) yields:

$$\bar{\epsilon} = \frac{2}{\sqrt{3}} \int \left(\frac{\dot{\epsilon}_x^2 + \dot{\epsilon}_y^2}{2} + \dot{\epsilon}_{xy}^2 \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} \frac{(X_t^2 + Y_t^2)^{\frac{1}{2}}}{Y_t (v_x^2 + v_y^2)^{\frac{1}{2}}} dy \quad (C.5)$$

Changing dy into dt gives:

$$\bar{\epsilon} = \frac{2}{\sqrt{3}} \int_0^1 \left(\frac{\dot{\epsilon}_x^2 + \dot{\epsilon}_y^2}{2} + \dot{\epsilon}_{xy}^2 \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} \frac{(X_t^2 + Y_t^2)^{\frac{1}{2}}}{Y_t (v_x^2 + v_y^2)^{\frac{1}{2}}} Y_t dt \quad (C.6)$$

Finally simplifying, the strain induced in the deforming region is given by:

$$\bar{\varepsilon}_{stream} = \bar{\varepsilon} = \frac{2}{\sqrt{3}} \int_0^1 \left(\frac{\dot{\varepsilon}_x^2 + \dot{\varepsilon}_y^2}{2} + \dot{\varepsilon}_{xy}^2 \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} \frac{(X_t^2 + Y_t^2)^{\frac{1}{2}}}{(v_x^2 + v_y^2)^{\frac{1}{2}}} dt \quad (C.7)$$

Strain induced at entry and exit discontinuity surfaces:

In the entry and exit shear surfaces there are some strains which are obtained by dividing the velocity discontinuity by the perpendicular component of the velocity to the shear surface as follows:

$$\gamma_i = \gamma_0 = \frac{|\Delta v|}{v_0 \cos \psi_1} = \frac{|\Delta v|}{v_0 \cos \left(\frac{v \psi}{2} \right)} = \left| \tan \left((r - v) \frac{\psi}{2} \right) + \tan \left(\frac{v \psi}{2} \right) \right| \quad (C.8)$$

where γ_i and γ_0 are the shear strains in surfaces EE and DD . The equivalent strain is therefore given by:

$$\varepsilon_{si} = \varepsilon_{so} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{3}} \left| \tan \left((r - v) \frac{\psi}{2} \right) + \tan \left(\frac{v \psi}{2} \right) \right| \quad (C.9)$$

Hence the total strain induced in the material is given by:

$$\bar{\varepsilon}_{ave} = \bar{\varepsilon}_s + \bar{\varepsilon}_{stream} \quad (C.10)$$